

Test protocol of the 6MCT adapted from Jansen et al (2012) [1]

General procedures

Equipment:

1. Cycle ergometer (Corival Pediatric, Lode BV, Groningen, Netherlands or Corival CPET, Lode BV, Groningen, Netherlands).
2. Upper arm sensor (Polar Verity Sense, Polar, Kempele, Finland).
3. Borg scale 6-20 for perceived exertion.

Set up:

1. The test should be performed in a quiet room, preferably without any family or friends in the room.
2. Assessor sits next to the participant.
3. The cycle ergometer is adjusted according to the patient's height.
4. It should set the lowest possible workload.

Test procedure:

1. Briefly demonstrate the cycling exercise and allow a short practical test.
2. A 10-minute rest period should be given prior to the test.
3. Record heart rate and level of perceived exertion.
4. Read the following statement: *“You will cycle as fast as possible and keep this up for 6 minutes. Try to continue until I tell you to that you have finished. You are allowed to rest, but try to continue for the whole 6 minutes.”*
5. The assessor should inform the participant about the time completed and left, and about the amount of revolutions cycled.
6. The assessor records the number of revolutions every minute.
7. The assessor should give verbal encouragements to maintain attention and to complete the test 15 s throughout the exercise.
8. Encouragement comments could be:
 - (a) *“You’re doing a great job! Keep going!”*
 - (b) *“Wow, you’re doing great! Keep going!”*
 - (c) *“You’re doing great, only 3 minutes left! Keep going!”*

9. At the final 10 seconds of the test, the assessor should count down.
10. Record the total number of revolutions cycled, heart rate and perceived exertion at 6 minutes.

Determining a valid test:

1. A test is valid if the participant completes or discontinues the test due to fatigue.
2. A test is invalid if the participant:
 - (a) Discontinues the test due reasons other than fatigue (such as noncompliance or injury).
 - (b) Did not follow the instructions.

References

1. Jansen, M. *et al.* The assisted 6-minute cycling test to assess endurance in children with a neuromuscular disorder. *Muscle & nerve* **46**, 520–530; 10.1002/mus.23369 (2012).